

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Segmental retention models for representing the hydraulic properties of evolving structured soils

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Abstract

Common parametrizations of soil hydraulic properties rely on unimodal curves, which cannot accurately represent the properties of many macroporous, aggregated, mixed, or compacted soils. Multimodal hydraulic curves are increasingly used to represent these structured soils in eco-hydrological models, but the dynamics of the processes that shape soil structure—and the resulting dynamics of soil hydraulic properties—are often neglected. In cases such as compaction recovery, where the structure-shaping process can be modeled, coupling the evolving pore volumes to soil hydraulic properties in a physically based way remains challenging. Here, we show how modeled or estimated soil structure evolution, when expressed as a time series of porosities in a few pore size classes, can be assimilated into established models of soil hydraulic properties. Our method relies on the division of retention models into smooth segments, whose water contents can be independently adjusted. We apply the approach to examples of modeled soil structure evolution from the published literature: one describing soil structure recovery after compaction and one describing structure formation as a result of organic amendment. In the cases considered, the estimated soil hydraulic conductivity varies more strongly than the modeled porosity which drives it. This shows that transport-related soil functions can be impacted longer (after compaction) or sooner (after amendment) than suggested by the evolution of structural metrics such as porosity. In general, modeling the evolution of soil hydraulic properties in cases such as these paves the way for holistic, process-based modeling of land management practices and their impact on soil functioning.

Plain Language Summary

Computer simulations of water propagation in the soil allow researchers to assess the risk of floods, optimize the irrigation of crops, or understand the effects of climate change on food production and water availability. These simulations use mathematical functions to describe how much water is stored in the soil and how fast it flows

Abbreviation: SOM, soil organic matter.

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under different conditions. Over the course of a typical simulation, these functions do not change, which makes it difficult to account for processes that significantly affect the capacity of soil to store and conduct water, such as soil freezing, plowing, spreading of manure, or the compression of soil by heavy machinery. Here, we introduce soil water storage and conductivity functions that can evolve in time as dictated by simulations or measurements of such soil-changing processes. Using these functions, we show that soil water propagation may be affected sooner after spreading amendments and longer after soil compaction than previously thought.

1 | INTRODUCTION

The parametrizations of soil hydraulic properties in many soil-crop, ecosystem, and land-surface models rely on unimodal hydraulic curves. However, highly structured soils (macroporous, aggregated, mixed, or compacted) whose properties cannot be described well with unimodal curves are widespread (Durner, 1994, and the references therein). Eco-hydrological models begin to account for that by incorporating piecewise (Jarvis et al., 2024) and multimodal (Bonetti et al., 2021; Fatichi et al., 2020) soil hydraulic property models, as well as dual-porosity and dual-permeability formulations (Šimúnek et al., 2003).

Unlike soil texture, soil structure is a dynamical property. It forms due to bioturbation, wetting and freezing cycles, or the accumulation of organic matter and it responds strongly to land management practices (Meurer, Barron et al., 2020). When representing structured soils, it is worthwhile to attempt to capture the nonstationarity of the structure-forming processes and the resulting time dependence of the soil hydraulic properties. Representing the latter can significantly improve the accuracy of eco-hydrological simulations (Chandrasekhar et al., 2018; Geris et al., 2021) and is especially important in the face of rapid global change (Robinson et al., 2019; Sullivan et al., 2022).

Evolution of structured soils changes many soil parameters, including soil volume, wetting properties, porosity, and connectivity of the soil pores. Among these, moisture-induced soil volume changes in clays are relatively well understood (Stewart et al., 2016) and have been subject to process-based modeling since a long time (Bronswijk, 1988; Jarvis, 1989). Modeling the evolution of pore volume (compaction/decompaction dynamics) in nonexpansive soils is a newer development, which could allow eco-hydrological models to incorporate structure-forming processes that are especially relevant for global change mitigation and adaptation. These include tillage (Or et al., 2000) and organic matter sequestration (König et al., 2023; Meurer, Chenu et al., 2020), bioturbation (Flores et al., 2021; Meurer, Barron et al., 2020), and mechanical compaction (Romero-Ruiz et al., 2023; Jha et al., 2023). However, for many of the above

processes it is not yet clear how to couple the relevant compaction/decompaction model with numerical soil hydrology schemes in a physically based way.

Here, we demonstrate an approach to incorporating modeled pore volume dynamics into existing retention–conductivity models, using the van Genuchten–Mualem model as an example. Our approach consists of dividing a site-specific retention curve into segments that are individually scaled to represent (de)compaction, and estimating hydraulic conductivity based on the evolving retention curve. Such an approach is suitable for compaction/decompaction dynamics expressed as time series of porosities—in a few predetermined size classes—which can come from a soil structure model (Flores et al., 2021; Jarvis et al., 2024; Meurer, Barron et al., 2020; Meurer, Chenu et al., 2020) or can be estimated using measured proxies such as soil bulk density and organic matter content (Arya & Paris, 1981; Gupta & Larson, 1979; Jensen et al., 2015; Rawls et al., 1983). We demonstrate the method using two examples: measured and modeled soil structure evolution following compaction by field traffic and simulated soil aggregation resulting from long-term organic amendment.

2 | METHODS AND DATA

2.1 | Segmental water retention curve

We begin by dividing the pore space into N size classes, with the i th class containing pores with radius between r_{i-1} and r_i . In practice, the number of classes and the threshold radii will be determined by the method used to simulate or estimate the evolution of pore space over time. For example, when estimating the effect of bioturbation on soil hydraulic properties, we will use the results of Meurer, Barron et al. (2020), whose model divides the pores space into $N = 3$ size classes separated by $r_1 = 15 \mu\text{m}$ and $r_2 = 50 \mu\text{m}$. In this section, to demonstrate the flexibility of our approach, we use $N = 5$ size classes based on the soil ecology model of Flores et al. (2021), even though this represents very detailed soil structure information that may rarely be

available in practice. These classes are delineated by pore radii of 50 nm, 1 μm , 20 μm , and 0.5 mm.

In its initial state, the soil is described by a retention curve $\theta(p)$, where $p = \log |h|$ is logarithmic pressure head (using natural logarithm and h in meters). The initial state can correspond to reconstituted or to structured soil, depending on the compaction/decompaction scenario. If the initial retention curve is measured, it must be fitted or interpolated so that $\theta(p)$ is defined for all p . Any interpolation method or empirical retention model can be used, but models with a nonvanishing derivative, such as the one of van Genuchten (1980), will offer the largest flexibility. (Models with a vanishing derivative, such as Brooks–Corey, can be used as long as no pore size class lies entirely above the air-entry value.) In the examples shown in Figures 1 and 2, $\theta(p)$ will be a van Genuchten curve using the Carsel and Parrish (1988) parameterization of silt loam.

FIGURE 1 A van Genuchten water retention curve for silt loam (Carsel & Parrish, 1988) decomposed into segments (dashed), with different colors corresponding to different pore size classes. Thin vertical lines show the pressure head values corresponding to boundaries between pore size classes.

FIGURE 2 Clipping functions used to construct the segments in Figure 1. The black line in the background is the identity line.

Core Ideas

- We show a method for dividing existing retention curves into smooth sub-curves corresponding to pore size classes.
- To represent an evolving soil structure, we scale the sub-curves and sum them to form a composite retention curve.
- We estimate the effect of (de)compaction on permeability using the composite retention curve and the Mualem model.
- We apply the approach to modeled response of soil structure to mechanical compaction and to organic amendments.

We use the capillary bundle conceptual model, in which soil pores saturate monotonically from smallest to largest as the absolute value of pressure head decreases. This allows us to identify each pore size class with a range of pressure heads at which the pores of the class are partially saturated. In this model, pore size class i corresponds to log pressure head values between p_{i-1} and p_i , where $p_i = \log(2\lambda_c^2/r_i)$ and λ_c is the water capillary length equal to 2.73 mm in standard conditions. This allows us to calculate the initial porosities ϕ_i in each class,

$$\phi_i = \theta(p_i) - \theta(p_{i-1}). \quad (1)$$

For the first pore size class (i.e., the smallest pores) we take $\phi_1 = \theta(p_1) - \theta_r$, where θ_r is the residual water content in the initial state.

As a result of compaction/decompaction dynamics, the porosities in each class will change from the initial values ϕ_i to time-dependent values $\phi_i^*(t)$. In the remainder of the subsection, we will construct a retention curve $\theta^*(t, p)$ based on $\theta(p)$ that is consistent with the new porosities $\phi_i^*(t)$ at all times. Specifically, we want $\theta^*(t, p)$ to satisfy

$$\phi_i^*(t) \approx \theta^*(t, p_i) - \theta^*(t, p_{i-1}) \quad (2)$$

and $\phi_1^*(t) \approx \theta^*(t, p_1) - \theta_r$, where we assume that the residual water content is not affected by (de)compaction.

To construct the new retention curve, we divide $\theta(p)$ into weakly overlapping segments $\theta_i(p)$, one for each pore size class, as shown in Figure 1. These segments will then be individually scaled to satisfy condition (2) at all times. The segments should correspond as closely as possible to the pore size classes; That is, $\theta_i(p)$ should be approximately 0 when the pores of class i are dry and approximately equal to ϕ_i when they are saturated. When added together, the segments should closely approximate the original curve $\theta(p)$. Finally, $\theta_i(p)$

ought to be smooth and have analytical formulas that are easily differentiable, as derivatives of the water retention curve enter statistical permeability models.

We obtain the segments from the original retention curve by modifying its argument with specially constructed clipping functions $f_i(p)$,

$$\theta_i(p) = \theta(f_i(p)) - \theta(p_{i-1}). \quad (3)$$

In Equation (3), using function composition $\theta(f_i(p))$ makes the derivatives of the segments easy to calculate using the chain rule, and subtracting $\theta(p_{i-1})$ (θ_r for the first size class) will ensure that the segments have zero residual water content.

The segments must approximate the original retention curve for pressure heads corresponding to their pore size class and be constant otherwise. This means that the clipping functions must approximate the identity $f_i(p) \approx p$ within the pressure head range corresponding to their pore size class and be constant otherwise. An example set of clipping functions, corresponding to the retention segments from Figure 1, is shown in Figure 2.

The clipping functions can be constructed from any S-shaped or “smooth step” function by applying geometrical transformations. Specifically, the midpoint of the step function must be positioned on the 1:1 identity line, the function must be scaled horizontally to set the derivative at the midpoint to 1, and the result must be scaled vertically to avoid gaps between consecutive $f_i(p)$. Starting from a step function $s(x)$ that changes monotonically from 0 for $x = 0$, through $1/2$ for $x = 1/2$, to 1 for $x = 1$, applying the above transformations gives

$$f_i(p) = 2p_i^- s\left(\frac{p - p_i^+}{2p_i^- s'} + \frac{1}{2}\right) + p_i, \quad (4)$$

where s' is the derivative of $s(x)$ at the midpoint, $p_i^+ = (p_{i-1} + p_i)/2$ is the center, and $p_i^- = (p_{i-1} - p_i)/2$ is the half-width of the log pressure head range of size class i . In Equation (4), adding $-p_i^+ + 1/2$ to the argument of $s(x)$ translates its midpoint horizontally from $1/2$ to p_i^+ , multiplying $s(x)$ by $2p_i^-$ sets the desired height of the step, dividing the argument by $2p_i^- s'$ sets the derivative at the midpoint to 1, and adding p_i translates the midpoint vertically.

The choice of the smooth step function $s(x)$ in Equation (4) is arbitrary. We use the following truncated polynomial, which is among the simplest functions with the desired form:

$$s(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & x \leq 0, \\ 3x^2 - 2x^3 & 0 < x \leq 1, \\ 1 & 1 < x. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The clipping functions of the smallest and largest size classes should saturate only at one end (see Figure 2), and

must be constructed accordingly. For the smallest size class, we first obtain a “smooth floor” function by replacing the upper half of $s(x)$ with a linear function. That is, we take $s(x) = (3x - 1/2)/2$ for $x > 1/2$. We then obtain f_1 from Equation (4), by choosing $p_1^- = p_2^-$ (to match the smoothness of f_1 and f_2) and $p_1^+ = p_1 + p_2^-$ (to close the gap between f_1 and f_2). The clipping function f_N of the largest size class is constructed analogously, using a “smooth ceiling” function obtained by replacing the $x < 1/2$ half of $s(x)$ with the same linear function as before.

Finally, we construct the new retention curve $\theta^*(t, p)$ from the segments after scaling them by (de)compaction factors $\phi_i^*(t)/\phi_i$,

$$\theta^*(t, p) = \theta_r + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\phi_i^*(t)}{\phi_i} \theta_i(p). \quad (6)$$

As shown in Figure 1, with (de)compaction factors equal to 1, $\theta^*(t, p)$ closely approximates the initial retention curve $\theta(p)$.

2.2 | Hydraulic conductivity curve

The hydraulic conductivity of the soil in its initial state is $K(p)$, of which we assume that at least the value K_s at saturation is known. Based on these and on the time-dependent retention curve $\theta^*(t, p)$, we will estimate the full (saturated and unsaturated) conductivity $K^*(t, p)$ during or following (de)compaction.

When estimating $K^*(t, p)$, we must ensure that (de)compacting pores in a given size class does not affect the hydraulic conductivity at pressure heads for which these pores are dry. For instance, (de)compacting macropores should not affect the dry end of the conductivity curve. To achieve this, the approaches we use to estimate the saturated and relative hydraulic conductivities must act in concert: If saturated conductivity increases as a result of decompacting macropores, relative conductivity at the dry end must decrease by the same amount to keep the net dry-end conductivity constant. This significantly limits which approaches we can use to estimate saturated conductivity, ruling out pedotransfer functions or estimates based on the Kozeny–Carman equation (Zhang & Schaap, 2019).

We will estimate the relative hydraulic conductivity using the model of Mualem (1976). To satisfy the requirement discussed above, we must estimate the saturated hydraulic conductivity following Mishra and Parker (1990) by integrating the Mualem model to saturation. In this approach, the full conductivity curve is given by

$$K^*(t, p) = M(\theta^*(t, p) - \theta_r)^l \left(\int_p^\infty \frac{d\theta^*}{dh} dp' \right)^2, \quad (7)$$

where M and l are empirical constants (without a clear physical interpretation), which depend on the soil, but do not change during compaction/decompaction dynamics. Allowing M and l to depend on the soil is likely to improve the accuracy of the estimate compared to the original estimate of Mishra and Parker (1990) with fixed M and l , which has been criticized for insufficient accuracy (Ghanbarian et al., 2017).

To determine M and l for a given soil, we fit the equivalent of Equation (7)—with $\theta(p)$ in place of $\theta^*(t, p)$ —to the initial conductivity curve $K(p)$ if it is known. If only the initial saturated conductivity K_s is known, we must assume a value for l ($1/2$ being a typical choice) and find M from the equivalent of Equation (7) by evaluating the integral over $\theta(p)$. If $\theta(p)$ is a van Genuchten curve with saturated water content θ_s and parameter α , the integral can be calculated analytically giving $M = K_s / [\alpha^2 (\theta_s - \theta_r)^{l+2}]$.

2.3 | Modeled evolution of structured soils

We will use the segmental retention curve with Equation (7) to analyze the evolution of soil hydraulic properties resulting from bioturbation and from long-term organic amendment. The two case studies are based on simulations performed by Meurer, Barron et al. (2020) and Meurer, Chenu et al. (2020) using compaction/decompaction models formulated in the respective papers.

Meurer, Barron et al. (2020) simulate the compaction/decompaction effects of earthworm bioturbation using a nonlinear model with pore volumes as the main dynamic variables. They use three size classes corresponding to micropores ($r < 15 \mu\text{m}$), mesopores ($15 \mu\text{m} < r < 50 \mu\text{m}$), and macropores ($50 \mu\text{m} < r$). The pore volumes are driven by changes in the volume of soil ingested by earthworms and in the volume of their casts.

Using their model, Meurer, Barron et al. (2020) simulate the recovery of macroporous soil following severe traffic compaction at the Soil Structure Observatory in Zürich, Switzerland (Keller et al., 2017). To estimate the corresponding evolution of soil hydraulic properties, we start with an initial retention curve $\theta(p)$ obtained using the Rosetta 3 pedotransfer function (Zhang & Schaap, 2017, via the web interface developed by Todd Skaggs—USDA Agricultural Research Service). We parameterize $\theta(p)$ using soil texture and bulk density measured at the site at 0–0.2 m depth (Keller et al., 2017), and we average the retention parameters obtained for the three blocks of the experiment. To calculate the porosities $\phi_i^*(t)$ before and immediately after compaction, we use the measurements of total porosity and air-filled porosity at 10 cm depth (Keller et al., 2017). The porosities 1 year and 2 years after compaction are simulated and taken from figure 7 in Meurer, Barron et al. (2020). We use only the first 2 years of the simulation, as the simulated porosities are already

very close to equilibrium by year 2. Since no unsaturated hydraulic conductivity measurements are readily available for this site, we take $l = 1/2$ and we calculate M from the saturated hydraulic conductivity measured prior to compaction at 0.1 m depth (Keller et al., 2017).

Meurer, Chenu et al. (2020) simulate the compaction/decompaction effects of organic soil amendments using a nonlinear model based on the Introductory Carbon Balance Model (Andren & Katterer, 1997). The main dynamic variables in the model are the masses of four soil organic matter (SOM) pools: younger and older organic matter stored either in contact with the mesopore network ($2.5 \mu\text{m} < r < 50 \mu\text{m}$) or partially protected in the micropores ($r < 2.5 \mu\text{m}$). The SOM pools are driven by above-ground inputs (amendments and litter), which enter the mesopore domain, and by below-ground inputs (roots and their exudates), which are split between micro- and mesopores in proportion to their volumes. The volumes of micropores and mesopores are calculated based on the amount of SOM they contain, assuming that pore volumes increase linearly with SOM volumes due to aggregation. Macropores ($50 \mu\text{m} < r$) are also represented in the model, but their volume is taken to be a constant fraction of the total soil volume.

Using their model, Meurer, Chenu et al. (2020) simulate the effect of long-term organic amendment on the evolution of soil structure at the Ultuna experiment in Uppsala, Sweden (Kirchmann et al., 1994). To estimate the corresponding evolution of soil hydraulic properties, we take a van Genuchten curve with parameters $\alpha = 4.4 \text{ m}^{-1}$, $n = 1.073$, $\theta_s = 0.407$, and $\theta_r = 0$ as the initial retention curve $\theta(p)$. These parameters were fitted by Meurer, Chenu et al. (2020) to measurements made at the site in 1969, with the exception of n , which was assumed to be constant throughout the experiment and was determined based on measurements from 2019. The simulated evolution of soil structure is given by the time series of microporosity $\phi_{\text{mic}}^*(t)$ and of matrix porosity $\phi_{\text{mat}}^*(t)$ (i.e., the sum of microporosity and mesoporosity). We take the former from figure 8 in Meurer, Chenu et al. (2020) and calculate the latter from SOM concentration shown in the same figure. (To do this, we use their Eq. 13 with the total mass of SOM calculated using their Eq. 17 and the soil layer thickness calculated using their Eq. 12.) The initial values of these time series, $\phi_{\text{mic}}^*(1956)$ and $\phi_{\text{mat}}^*(1956)$, differ from the porosities ϕ_{mic} and ϕ_{mat} that can be obtained from the initial retention curve $\theta(p)$. This could be because the earliest retention measurements were made 13 years after the start of the experiment and outside of the experimental plots (Meurer, Chenu et al., 2020), which could have complicated the initialization of the soil structure model. To preserve the soil structure dynamics given by the time series $\phi_{\text{mic}}^*(t)$ and $\phi_{\text{mat}}^*(t)$, but start from the measured retention curve $\theta(p)$, we rescale $\phi_{\text{mic}}^*(t)$ by $\phi_{\text{mic}} / \phi_{\text{mic}}^*(1956)$ and $\phi_{\text{mat}}^*(t)$ by $\phi_{\text{mat}} / \phi_{\text{mat}}^*(1956)$. To estimate the hydraulic

FIGURE 3 Evolution of soil hydraulic properties due to traffic compaction and the following recovery due to earthworm bioturbation. Based on measurements from the Soil Structure Observatory (Keller et al., 2017) and on the simulation of Meurer, Barron et al. (2020).

conductivity, we again assume $l = 1/2$ and calculate M from the saturated hydraulic conductivity estimated with Rosetta 3 based on texture and bulk density measured at the site.

3 | RESULTS

3.1 | Evolution of soil hydraulic properties due to and following traffic compaction

In this section, we estimate the evolution of the hydraulic properties of macroporous silt loam as it undergoes and recovers from severe traffic compaction. The effect of the initial compaction on pore volumes is based on measurements performed at the Soil Structure Observatory (Keller et al., 2017), whereas the recovery is based on a simulation performed by Meurer, Barron et al. (2020) for this site using their model of earthworm bioturbation (as described in Section 2.3).

The experimental site has been established on a conventionally managed arable field, which has been under grass–clover–alfalfa ley for 1 year prior to compaction (Keller et al., 2017). Just before compaction, the micro- and mesoporosities were essentially at their textural values (see “initial” panel in Figure 3), whereas the macropores are significantly

decompacted due to the combined effects of plant roots and bioturbation.

The soil at the site was compacted under moist conditions by three passes track-by-track with a two-axle vehicle with an average wheel load of 8 metric ton (Keller et al., 2017). As a result, mesopores were compacted to 47% of their original volume ratio, but since this class is rather narrowly defined in the model of Meurer, Barron et al. (2020), the corresponding effect on unsaturated conductivity is not significant (see “compacted” panel in Figure 3). At the same time, compaction decreased macroporosity by 64% and we estimate that saturated conductivity decreased by 85% as a result. This is relatively close to the 73% decrease of saturated conductivity that was measured in the field (Keller et al., 2017).

After compaction, vegetation in the relevant experimental plots was suppressed by periodic application of glyphosate (Keller et al., 2017). The post-compaction recovery is thus due to faunal bioturbation and possibly due to abiotic factors, which were not included in the simulation of the recovery. Two years after compaction, the macroporosity has largely reached a steady state, recovering to 73% of its original value. However, we estimate that this corresponds to a saturated conductivity of only about half (53%) of its original value

FIGURE 4 Evolution of soil hydraulic properties in the bare fallow and animal manure treatments of a long-term soil organic matter experiment. Based on the simulation of Meurer, Chenu et al. (2020) for the Ultuna trial (Kirchmann et al., 1994).

(see “after 2 years” panel in Figure 3; limited recovery is also suggested by geoelectrical measurements performed at the site Romero-Ruiz et al., 2022). This suggests that the soil at this site might not recover its pre-compaction hydraulic properties due to faunal bioturbation alone. A complete unaided recovery could require the action of plant roots as well, whose effect on soil structure, however, is much slower than that of faunal bioturbation (Meurer, Barron et al., 2020).

3.2 | Evolution of soil hydraulic properties due to long-term organic amendment

In this section, we analyze the evolution of soil hydraulic properties in two contrasting treatments—animal manure amendment and bare fallow—in the Ultuna long-term trial (Kirchmann et al., 1994). We estimate the hydraulic properties based on the compaction/decompaction dynamics simulated for this site by Meurer, Chenu et al. (2020) using their model of SOM-induced aggregation (as described in Section 2.3).

In the simulation of Meurer, Chenu et al. (2020), micropore SOM and porosity decrease in both treatments by a similar amount. Meurer, Chenu et al. (2020) link this decrease to tillage, which is practiced in both treatments, and which they

estimate results in a net carbon flow to the mesopore domain. The resulting loss of micropore aggregation decreases microporosity by 12% over the course of the experiment, which we estimate decreases unsaturated hydraulic conductivity by about 27% below field capacity (see Figure 4).

Meurer, Chenu et al. (2020) simulate that mesopore SOM content increases in both treatments, although to a different extent. In the fallow plots, SOM input due to mixing increases mesopore aggregation and porosity by 44%, leading to an estimated increase of unsaturated conductivity at $h = -0.3$ m by a factor of 1.8 compared to the initial state. In the manured plots, SOM originating from micropores, plant input, and the amendment increases porosity and unsaturated conductivity (at $h = -0.4$ m), respectively, by 82% and a factor of 2.8.

4 | DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

We have demonstrated how segmentation of the soil water retention curve can be used to trace the evolution of hydraulic properties resulting from compaction/decompaction dynamics. The segmentation method does not introduce any parameters in addition to the time-dependent porosities, and it can use any retention model as a starting point. This means that

it can be implemented even in complex models without the need for model retuning.

When implemented, the segmentation method provides adjustable porosities for a chosen number of pore size classes. These porosities can be linked to models describing soil structure evolution due to processes such as tillage, organic matter sequestration, bioturbation, and mechanical compaction. We have analyzed cases in which these processes led to a six-fold decrease of saturated hydraulic conductivity (due to compaction) or to a three-fold increase of unsaturated conductivity (due to organic amendment). Comparable variations of hydraulic conductivity have been linked to significant effects on infiltration and field water storage (Alletto et al., 2015; Wahren et al., 2009; Xu & Mermoud, 2003).

Compared to adjusting the parameters of existing retention models to represent compaction/decompaction (e.g., Jarvis et al., 2024; Meurer, Barron et al., 2020), segmentation offers two advantages. First, changing the porosity in one size class does not change the shape of the hydraulic curves in other classes. Second, it can describe the evolution from unstructured to structured soil, with the retention curve evolving smoothly from a unimodal function to a multimodal one (and vice versa).

The segmentation approach can represent the compaction of unstructured soil, and as such has broader applicability than the matrix-and-macropores superposition model (Durner, 1994; Othmer et al., 1991). It is also more parsimonious, as the retention sub-curves inherit their shape from the original unstructured soil and do not have to be individually parameterized.

Similarly to other approaches using superposition models to describe the effect of soil structure on soil hydraulic properties (Fatichi et al., 2020), the segmentation method as presented neglects changes in pore connectivity and tortuosity. Per-class tortuosity factors could be included in Equation (7), and their change upon (de)compaction estimated using empirical approaches (Assouline & Or, 2008, and the references therein). However, we think that a further increase in the complexity of the presented approach is not justified given the scarcity of suitable evaluation data.

Evaluation data is limited as, in the case studies shown, only the estimate of saturated conductivity immediately after traffic compaction could be compared to measurements made on site. Subsequent estimates in that case study are not comparable to measurements, because the underlying compaction/decompaction simulation lacks the significant background variability that was observed in all treatments (Meurer, Barron et al., 2020). For the Ultuna trial, freely available conductivity data is not sufficient for any comparisons.

Comprehensively evaluating a model like ours would require paired retention and conductivity measurements on undisturbed samples over a strong soil structure gradient in time or in space. Such data is not readily available, but new

developments in in situ measurements of soil hydraulic properties (Fu et al., 2021; Špongrová et al., 2009; Tian et al., 2018; Yu et al., 2021) might make it easier to obtain. In the absence of such observations, small-scale simulations using lattice Boltzmann (Liu et al., 2016) or pore-network models (Xiong et al., 2016) could perhaps prove valuable in constraining the effects of evolving pore space on soil water flow.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Filip Kialka: Methodology; software; writing—original draft; funding acquisition. **Omar Flores:** Writing—review and editing. **Kim Naudts:** Writing—review and editing. **Sebastiaan Luyssaert:** Conceptualization; writing—review and editing; funding acquisition. **Bertrand Guenet:** Conceptualization; writing—review and editing; supervision; funding acquisition.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The code and data used to generate the figures are available on GitHub at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13737543>.

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REFERENCES

- Alletto, L., Pot, V., Giuliano, S., Costes, M., Perdrioux, F., & Justes, E. (2015). Temporal variation in soil physical properties improves the water dynamics modeling in a conventionally-tilled soil. *Geoderma*, 243–244, 18–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2014.12.006>
- Andrén, O., & Käätterer, T. (1997). ICBM: The Introductory Carbon Balance Model for exploration of soil carbon balances. *Ecological Applications*, 7(4), 1226–1236. [https://doi.org/10.1890/1051-0761\(1997\)007\[1226:ITICBM\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/1051-0761(1997)007[1226:ITICBM]2.0.CO;2)
- Arya, L. M., & Paris, J. F. (1981). A physicoempirical model to predict the soil moisture characteristic from particle-size distribution and bulk density data. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 45(6), 1023–1030. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj1981.03615995004500060004x>

- Assouline, S., & Or, D. (2008). Air entry-based characteristic length for estimation of permeability of variably compacted earth materials. *Water Resources Research*, 44(11), W11403. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2008WR006937>
- Bonetti, S., Wei, Z., & Or, D. (2021). A framework for quantifying hydrologic effects of soil structure across scales. *Communications Earth & Environment*, 2(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-021-00180-0>
- Bronswijk, J. J. B. (1988). Modeling of water balance, cracking and subsidence of clay soils. *Journal of Hydrology*, 97(3), 199–212. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1694\(88\)90115-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1694(88)90115-1)
- Carsel, R. F., & Parrish, R. S. (1988). Developing joint probability distributions of soil water retention characteristics. *Water Resources Research*, 24(5), 755–769. <https://doi.org/10.1029/WR024i005p00755>
- Chandrasekhar, P., Kreiselmeier, J., Schwen, A., Weninger, T., Julich, S., Feger, K.-H., & Schwärzel, K. (2018). Why we should include soil structural dynamics of agricultural soils in hydrological models. *Water*, 10(12), 1862. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w10121862>
- Durner, W. (1994). Hydraulic conductivity estimation for soils with heterogeneous pore structure. *Water Resources Research*, 30(2), 211–223. <https://doi.org/10.1029/93WR02676>
- Faticchi, S., Or, D., Walko, R., Vereecken, H., Young, M. H., Ghezzehei, T. A., Hengl, T., Kollet, S., Agam, N., & Avissar, R. (2020). Soil structure is an important omission in earth system models. *Nature Communications*, 11(1), 522. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-14411-z>
- Flores, O., Deckmyn, G., Yuste, J. C., Javaux, M., Uvarov, A., van der Linde, S., Vos, B. D., Vereecken, H., Jiménez, J., Vinduskova, O., & Schnepf, A. (2021). KEYLINK: Towards a more integrative soil representation for inclusion in ecosystem scale models—II: Model description, implementation and testing. *PeerJ*, 9, e10707. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.10707>
- Fu, Y., Lu, S., Ren, T., Horton, R., & Heitman, J. L. (2021). Estimating soil water retention curves from soil thermal conductivity measurements. *Journal of Hydrology*, 603, 127171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2021.127171>
- Geris, J., Verrot, L., Gao, L., Peng, X., Oyesiku-Blakemore, J., Smith, J. U., Hodson, M. E., McKenzie, B. M., Zhang, G., & Hallett, P. D. (2021). Importance of short-term temporal variability in soil physical properties for soil water modelling under different tillage practices. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 213, 105132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2021.105132>
- Ghanbarian, B., Hunt, A. G., Skaggs, T. H., & Jarvis, N. (2017). Upscaling soil saturated hydraulic conductivity from pore throat characteristics. *Advances in Water Resources*, 104, 105–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advwatres.2017.03.016>
- Gupta, S. C., & Larson, W. E. (1979). Estimating soil water retention characteristics from particle size distribution, organic matter percent, and bulk density. *Water Resources Research*, 15(6), 1633–1635. <https://doi.org/10.1029/WR015i006p01633>
- Jarvis, N. (1989). *CRACK: A model of water and solute movement in cracking clay soils* (Report No. 159). Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences. <https://res.slu.se/id/publ/125562>
- Jarvis, N., Coucheney, E., Lewan, E., Klöffel, T., Meurer, K. H. E., Keller, T., & Larsbo, M. (2024). Interactions between soil structure dynamics, hydrological processes, and organic matter cycling: A new soil-crop model. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 75(2), e13455. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13455>
- Jensen, D. K., Tuller, M., de Jonge, L. W., Arthur, E., & Moldrup, P. (2015). A new two-stage approach to predicting the soil water characteristic from saturation to oven-dryness. *Journal of Hydrology*, 521, 498–507. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2014.12.018>
- Jha, A., Bonetti, S., Smith, A. P., Souza, R., & Calabrese, S. (2023). Linking soil structure, hydraulic properties, and organic carbon dynamics: A holistic framework to study the impact of climate change and land management. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Biogeosciences*, 128(7), e2023JG007389. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023JG007389>
- Keller, T., Colombi, T., Ruiz, S., Manalili, M. P., Rek, J., Stadelmann, V., Wunderli, H., Breitenstein, D., Reiser, R., Oberholzer, H., Schymanski, S., Romero-Ruiz, A., Linde, N., Weisskopf, P., Walter, A., & Or, D. (2017). Long-term soil structure observatory for monitoring post-compaction evolution of soil structure. *Vadose Zone Journal*, 16(4), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.2136/vzj2016.11.0118>
- Kirchmann, H., Persson, J., & Carlgren, K. (1994). The Ultuna long-term soil organic matter experiment, 1956–1991. Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences.
- König, S., Weller, U., Betancur-Corredor, B., Lang, B., Reitz, T., Wiesmeier, M., Wollschläger, U., & Vogel, H.-J. (2023). BODIUM—A systemic approach to model the dynamics of soil functions. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 74(5), e13411. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13411>
- Liu, H., Kang, Q., Leonardi, C. R., Schmieschek, S., Narváez, A., Jones, B. D., Williams, J. R., Valocchi, A. J., & Harting, J. (2016). Multiphase lattice Boltzmann simulations for porous media applications. *Computational Geosciences*, 20(4), 777–805. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10596-015-9542-3>
- Meurer, K. H. E., Barron, J., Chenu, C., Coucheney, E., Fielding, M., Hallett, P., Herrmann, A. M., Keller, T., Koestel, J., Larsbo, M., Lewan, E., Or, D., Parsons, D., Parvin, N., Taylor, A., Vereecken, H., & Jarvis, N. (2020). A framework for modelling soil structure dynamics induced by biological activity. *Global Change Biology*, 26(10), 5382–5403. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15289>
- Meurer, K. H. E., Chenu, C., Coucheney, E., Herrmann, A. M., Keller, T., Kätterer, T., Nimblad Svensson, D., & Jarvis, N. (2020). Modelling dynamic interactions between soil structure and the storage and turnover of soil organic matter. *Biogeosciences*, 17(20), 5025–5042. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-17-5025-2020>
- Mishra, S., & Parker, J. C. (1990). On the relation between saturated conductivity and capillary retention characteristics. *Groundwater*, 28(5), 775–777. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-6584.1990.tb01991.x>
- Mualem, Y. (1976). A new model for predicting the hydraulic conductivity of unsaturated porous media. *Water Resources Research*, 12(3), 513–522. <https://doi.org/10.1029/WR012i003p00513>
- Or, D., Leij, F. J., Snyder, V., & Ghezzehei, T. A. (2000). Stochastic model for posttillage soil pore space evolution. *Water Resources Research*, 36(7), 1641–1652. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2000WR900092>
- Othmer, H., Diekkrüger, B., & Kutilek, M. (1991). Bimodal porosity and unsaturated hydraulic conductivity. *Soil Science*, 152(3), 139–150. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00010694-199109000-00001>
- Rawls, W. J., Brakensiek, D. L., & Soni, B. (1983). Agricultural management effects on soil water processes part I: Soil water retention and green and ampt infiltration parameters. *Transactions of the ASAE*, 26(1), 1747–1752. <https://doi.org/10.13031/2013.33837>
- Robinson, D. A., Hopmans, J. W., Filipovic, V., van der Ploeg, M., Lebron, I., Jones, S. B., Reinsch, S., Jarvis, N., & Tuller, M. (2019). Global environmental changes impact soil hydraulic func-

- tions through biophysical feedbacks. *Global Change Biology*, 25(6), 1895–1904. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14626>
- Romero-Ruiz, A., Linde, N., Baron, L., Breitenstein, D., Keller, T., & Or, D. (2022). Lasting effects of soil compaction on soil water regime confirmed by geoelectrical monitoring. *Water Resources Research*, 58(2), e2021WR030696. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021WR030696>
- Romero-Ruiz, A., Monaghan, R., Milne, A., Coleman, K., Cardenas, L., Segura, C., & Whitmore, A. P. (2023). Modelling changes in soil structure caused by livestock treading. *Geoderma*, 431, 116331. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2023.116331>
- Šimůnek, J., Jarvis, N. J., van Genuchten, M. T., & Gärdenäs, A. (2003). Review and comparison of models for describing non-equilibrium and preferential flow and transport in the vadose zone. *Journal of Hydrology*, 272(1), 14–35. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694\(02\)00252-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694(02)00252-4)
- Špongrová, K., Kechavarzi, C., Dresser, M., Matula, S., & Godwin, R. J. (2009). Development of an automated tension infiltrometer for field use. *Vadose Zone Journal*, 8(3), 810–817. <https://doi.org/10.2136/vzj2008.0135>
- Stewart, R. D., Rupp, D. E., Abou Najm, M. R., & Selker, J. S. (2016). A unified model for soil shrinkage, subsidence, and cracking. *Vadose Zone Journal*, 15(3), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.2136/vzj2015.11.0146>
- Sullivan, P. L., Billings, S. A., Hirmas, D., Li, L., Zhang, X., Ziegler, S., Murenbeeld, K., Ajami, H., Guthrie, A., Singha, K., Giménez, D., Duro, A., Moreno, V., Flores, A., Cueva, A., Koop, Aronson, E. L., Barnard, H. R., Banwart, S. A., ... Wen, H. (2022). Embracing the dynamic nature of soil structure: A paradigm illuminating the role of life in critical zones of the Anthropocene. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 225, 103873. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2021.103873>
- Tian, Z., Kool, D., Ren, T., Horton, R., & Heitman, J. L. (2018). Determining in-situ unsaturated soil hydraulic conductivity at a fine depth scale with heat pulse and water potential sensors. *Journal of Hydrology*, 564, 802–810. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2018.07.052>
- van Genuchten, M. T. (1980). A closed-form equation for predicting the hydraulic conductivity of unsaturated soils. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 44(5), 892–898. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj1980.03615995004400050002x>
- Wahren, A., Feger, K.-H., Schwärzel, K., & Münch, A. (2009). Land-use effects on flood generation – considering soil hydraulic measurements in modelling. *Advances in Geosciences*, 21, 99–107. <https://doi.org/10.5194/adgeo-21-99-2009>
- Xiong, Q., Baychev, T. G., & Jivkov, A. P. (2016). Review of pore network modelling of porous media: Experimental characterisations, network constructions and applications to reactive transport. *Journal of Contaminant Hydrology*, 192, 101–117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconhyd.2016.07.002>
- Xu, D., & Mermoud, A. (2003). Modeling the soil water balance based on time-dependent hydraulic conductivity under different tillage practices. *Agricultural Water Management*, 63(2), 139–151. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-3774\(03\)00180-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-3774(03)00180-X)
- Yu, S., Xu, Q., Cheng, X., Xiang, Y., Zhu, Y., Yan, X., Wang, Z., Du, T., Wu, X., & Cheng, Q. (2021). In-situ determination of soil water retention curves in heterogeneous soil profiles with a novel dielectric tube sensor for measuring soil matric potential and water content. *Journal of Hydrology*, 603, 126829. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2021.126829>
- Zhang, Y., & Schaap, M. G. (2017). Weighted recalibration of the Rosetta pedotransfer model with improved estimates of hydraulic parameter distributions and summary statistics (Rosetta3). *Journal of Hydrology*, 547, 39–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2017.01.004>
- Zhang, Y., & Schaap, M. G. (2019). Estimation of saturated hydraulic conductivity with pedotransfer functions: A review. *Journal of Hydrology*, 575, 1011–1030. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2019.05.058>

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